

Table 2. Temperature range of photoperiod sensitivity in fertility alteration in PGMS.

Line	Low point (°C)	High point (°C)
Nongken 58 S	24	30
5088 S	22	30
7001 S	22	28
31111 S	22	28
1541 S	22	(28) ^a
Pei'ai 64 S	22	(24)
M901 S	24	(26)
HN5-2 S	24	(24)
8906 S	24	(26)
8902 S	28	30
8912 S	26	30
5047 S	26	(30)
9044 S	28	(32)
Shuangguang S	28	32
W6154 S	28	(28)

^aNumbers in parentheses were in other experiments.

The low HP-low LP group sterile lines (Pei'ai 64 S, M901 S, HN5-2 S, and 8906 S) have stable sterilities under long-day conditions (without impact of temperature) and under high temperature conditions (regardless of daylength). Their multiplications, however, are easily lost under short-day conditions when temperature rises occasionally. These PGMS lines can be used for producing hybrid seed in most rice-growing areas. Sterile lines can only be multiplied during certain seasons or at higher altitudes in tropical areas.

The high HP-high LP group sterile lines (8902 S, 8912 S, 5047 S, 9044 S, and Shuangguang S) can be multiplied easily under short-day conditions, but their sterilities are unstable under long-day conditions as temperature decreases. Because their sterilities are unstable, they are difficult to use in the two-line system. They can possibly be used in subtropical rice-growing areas of China.

The low HP-high LP group sterile lines (W6154 S and others) have stable sterilities under higher temperature without impact of photoperiod. Their sterilities, however, are unstable under long-day conditions when exposed to lower temperature. Their multiplication under short-day conditions can be affected when temperature rises occasionally. These lines can be used for hybrid seed production and multiplied during a specific season or at higher altitudes in tropical rice-growing areas. We do not recommend their use in the subtropics. ■

Inflorescence culture in rice

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We successfully induced calli and regenerated plants in salt-tolerant indica line IR31662-47-2-1 for exploitation of somaclonal variation. Young tillers were cut about 7-9 cm from the base of vigorous plants in pots. Tillers were thoroughly scrubbed with and dipped in 75% alcohol for 10 min. Leaf sheaths were stripped off under aseptic conditions.

Young inflorescences were divided into groups based on their length: DS₁ (0.5 cm), DS₂ (1 cm), DS₃ (2 cm), DS₄ (3 cm), DS₅ (4 cm), and DS₆ (5 cm). Inflorescences were cleaned with the commercial detergent Teepol (5% vol/vol) for 5 min, rinsed in water, sterilized with 0.1% aqueous HgCl₂ for 10 min, and then washed three times with sterile double-distilled water. Sterilized explants were placed on slant cultures with basal LS medium supplemented with 2,4-D and kinetin at rates of 0.5 (LS₁), 1 (LS₂), 1.5 (LS₃), and 2 (LS₄) mg/liter each, and on MS basal medium supplemented with naphthalene acetic acid and kinetin at rates of 0.5 (MS₁), 1

(MS₂), 1.5 (MS₃), and 2 (MS₄) mg/liter each.

Cultures were kept in total darkness at 25 ± 2 °C. After 28 d, portions of calli were subcultured on the same medium without hormone. Remaining calli were directly placed on regeneration medium (LS basal + 2 mg kinetin/liter + 0.5 mg indole acetic acid/liter). For subculturing, culture tubes were kept in total darkness; for regeneration, cultures were maintained under 16:8 h light:dark cycle. Light intensity was 2,000 lux.

LS₁, MS₁, MS₂, MS₃, and MS₄ failed to induce any calli, but direct plant regeneration without a visible callus stage was obtained in MS₂, MS₃, and MS₄ with 2-cm-long young inflorescences. LS₂, LS₃, and LS₄ induced callus formation. During peak callus formation, callus induction percentage and callus health varied significantly according to developmental stage of inflorescences (Table 1). Calli formed earliest in young inflorescences (0.5 and 1.0 cm), which grew vigorously and had high induction frequencies of healthy calli. Induction percentage was inversely proportional to developmental stage of the inflorescence. LS₃ was the best hormonal level for inducing calli.

In the subculturing experiment, all calli died within 16-22 d, suggesting

Table 1. Degree of callus-forming ability and callus health in IR31662-47-2-1.

Treatment	Inflorescence length (cm)	Callus induction (%)	Peak callus-forming period (d)	Callus health (1-6 scale) ^a
LS ₂	0.5	82	-	2
	1	78	-	1
	2	70	-	3
	3	68	-	3
	4	50	-	5
LS ₃	5	44	-	6
	0.5	100	12 - 15	1
	1	100	12 - 15	1
	2	90	16 - 18	2
	3	84	16 - 19	4
LS ₄	4	62	25 - 26	6
	5	52	40 - 42	6
	0.5	90	-	1
	1	86	-	1
	2	82	-	4
	3	74	-	5
	4	60	-	3
	5	47	-	3

^a1 = excellent, 2 - 3 = good, 4 - 5 = moderate, and 6 = poor.

Table 2. Regeneration ability of plants from inflorescence-derived calli of IR31662-47-2-1.

Explant length (cm)	Days to form green plantlet	Regeneration (%)
DS ₁ (0.5)	23	74.2
DS ₂ (1)	20	65.0
DS ₃ (2)	26	40.6
DS ₄ (3)	25	25.2
DS ₅ (4)	23	22.8
DS ₆ (5)	21	19.0

Pest resistance— diseases

Evolution of rice blast (BI) fungus based on cross-fertility of *Pyricularia grisea* Sac.

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We collected 500 monoconidial isolates of *P. grisea* from rice-growing regions of Yunnan Province, China. These isolates were crossed with standard isolates 57-R-33 (MAT1-1) and 57-R-28 (MAT1-2), both of which were isolated from *Eleusine coracana* (L.) Gaertn. Results showed that geographic environment and rice type influenced cross-fertility of *P. grisea*: in southern Yunnan, it was more than 60%, and in the high-altitude cold region where japonicas are grown, it was only 10%. Twenty-six isolates that produced perithecia and ascospores were selected for further study. (See table for location, hosts, mating type, perithecial formation by single culture of isolates, and rate of perfect state formation.)

Ten isolates of MAT1-1 were crossed with 16 isolates of MAT1-2. Although isolates crossed with the mating standard isolates produced ascospores, the cross-fertility of these isolates was remarkably different. Isolate YL 90-84 crossed with all fertile isolates. Y88-285 did not produce any ascospores in any cross combinations, although a few produced sterile perithecia. Number of

hormones might be an integral component of media for successful subcultures.

In the regeneration experiment, 2,4-D was completely withdrawn and replaced with IAA. Appearance of green plantlets was fastest with 1-cm-long young inflorescences and slowest with 2-cm-long inflorescences. Regeneration frequency notably varied with

developmental stage of the explant. Highest regeneration frequency occurred in 0.5-cm-long young inflorescences and lowest frequency in 5-cm-long inflorescences (Table 2).

Young inflorescences are a good source for rice tissue culture. They have efficient callus induction and redifferentiation frequencies. ■

perithecia produced varied greatly with combinations of isolates. In general, the fertile isolates with wide cross-fertility also showed higher cross-fertility, producing more perithecia and ascospores compared with other isolates.

Isolates with greatest mating competence, YL 90-84 (MAT1-2) and YL 90-71, YL 90-90, YL 90-80, YL 90-77, and others (MAT1-1), were all isolated from upland rice in Xishuangbanna, southern Yunnan province. Single cultures of these isolates, except YL 90-84, produced sterile perithecia on oatmeal agar at 22 °C with

continuous illumination. The process of perithecial formation conformed with the formation process of perithecium in mating and also the perithecium-like structure produced by single cultures of *Pyricularia* from *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn. and *E. coracana* (L.) Gaertn. The perithecia produced by single cultures had two common characteristics: they were derived from isolates with higher cross-fertility, and they formed two bands of perithecia. These isolates were all hermaphrodites. We speculate that *Pyricularia* might have evolved from

Location, host source, race, and mating type of *Pyricularia grisea*. Yunnan Province, China.

Isolate	Location	Host source		Race	Mating	P ^b	R ^c
		Variety	Type ^a				
YL 90-7	Mojiang	Dalixian 40	I	016-t	MAT1-2	-	40.0
YL 90-10	Mojiang	Luoping	?	136	MAT1-2	-	10.0
YL 90-11	Mojiang	Luoping	?	136	MAT1-2	-	20.0
YL 90-13	Mojiang	Luoping	?	036	MAT1-2	-	50.0
YL 90-175	Jingping	Gaoshanzaogu	?	106	MAT1-2	-	40.0
YL 90-51	Jingping	Luopinggu	?	016	MAT1-2	-	30.0
YL 90-52	Jingping	Luoping	?	117	MAT1-2	-	50.0
YL 90-84	Jinghong	Unknown	U	134-t	MAT1-2	-	100.0
YL 90-71	Jinghong	Unknown	U	102	MAT1-1	+	87.5
YL 90-74	Jinghong	Unknown	U	116	MAT1-1	+	43.8
YL 90-77	Jinghong	Unknown	U	102	MAT1-1	+	43.8
YL 90-80	Jinghong	Unknown	U	136-t	MAT1-1	+	62.5
YL 90-90	Jinghong	Unknown	U	116	MAT1-1	+	75.0
Y88-685	Maguang	D-you 63	I	0	MAT1-2	-	20.0
Y88-285	Liuku	Yunjing 134	J	017	MAT1-2	-	0.0
Y88-282	Liuku	Nuogu	J	037-t	MAT1-2	-	70.0
Y88-249	Tengchong	74-35	J	0	MAT1-2	-	40.0
13-1	Tengchong	74-35	J	0	MAT1-2	-	60.0
5-1	Qujing	Chujing 3	J	016-t	MAT1-2	-	30.0
5-2	Qujing	Chujing 3	J	016-t	MAT1-2	-	60.0
5-5	Qujing	Chujing 3	J	016-t	MAT1-2	-	30.0
45-1	Jinghong	Luexi	U	136	MAT1-1	-	6.3
45-2	Jinghong	Luexi	U	136	MAT1-1	-	12.5
45-3	Jinghong	Luexi	U	136	MAT1-1	-	18.8
45-4	Jinghong	Luexi	U	136	MAT1-1	-	18.8
45-5	Jinghong	Luexi	U	136	MAT1-1	-	37.5

^aI = indica, U = upland rice, J = japonica, ? = unknown. ^bP = perithecia production in single culture. + = produced, - = not produced. ^cR = rate of perfect state formation.